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THE RING OF POWER (STORY OF FRIENDSHIP AND TRUST)

Dr. Shreyasi Singh

There has always been a dialectical relationship between darkness and light. The Presence of one indicates the absence of the other. The existence of darkness is eternal. But a tiny streak of light is capable of ending the existence of darkness. Our past is a witness to this, the struggle between darkness and light has been going on for centuries. Humanity demands the Victory of light, but fighting against darkness demands a great sacrifice. This is the reason why I liked this series. Here man does not give up hope, He know that the enemy is stronger than him, but against darkness, only one flame is enough the art why is any great? thing, it in any art, man more importance to called great? greatness is not concreate thing, it is a feeling in any literature, in any arts, man reveals all his possibilities, gives more importance to his love than his hatred, dreams of Creation as opposed to destruction, that literature, that art, can only be called Classical.

The series begins with a discovery. The whole world has started to fell that the shadow of evil has disappeared. But 'Galadriel' does not believe it. She feels her conscience constantly telling her that the evil is not over, she is gathering more and more strength to make a grand comeback.

This story of good and evil is not new. Don't know how many sagas have been writing keeping this topic at the center, in which it has been shown that evil may be more powerful but victory is of good in the end. In the Indian context, the story of Ramayana and Mahabharata is a story of conflict, struggle and Victory between good and evil. We watch the Sun set every evening, as the night progresses, the darkness gets thicker. It is only after the deepest darkness that light enters. The spread of darkness is as natural as the spread of light. It depends on the will of the man that whom he would like to choose and your choices create your personality. It is not who you were, it is what you want to be? At the very beginning of the series, the essence of entire has been told through a short story. A stone sinkes in water because it can see only the darkness of the deep water. A boat floats because it sees the light of the sky, not the darkness of the depths. And those days will also come in history when the light of the sky and the light of the waves will guide the boat, which one is right? Would have to choose. The path of truth, the path of light is not so easy, some times you have to touch the dark to find the light. Galadriel is looking for Sauran. He is sure his not finished just changed his form but his own army rebels against him in the end. Galadriel also return home, left alone.

The story moves on and the next strong charcter in the story is Nori, she is a harfut, a race of dwarfs. But her caurage, her determination, her noble nature, her friendship turn her into one of the most beautiful female characters in the series. Nori's character had been my favourite Character Galadriel returns home, she and her crew are rewarded with the western lands but she does not want to go there, she jumps off the ship and is protected by a stranger in the endless sea. Here Nori also protects a stranger. Nori has a very big heart, her habit of helping people shows her best human qualities. She is ready to help any unknown person regardless of whether it will prove to be good or bad for her. Several subplots run concurrently in this film. A story based on

the friendship of Elf and Dwarves. The unbreakable bond of friendship that binels people of two different races together. Actually this series it a Unique story of mutual partnership, love and friendship.

The influence of darkness is slowly spreading evil is trying to overpower the good. Elves and humans form an alliance together to wage war against the darkness but forces of evil are too strong and they are defeated. His morale does not weaken even after losing.

The Series returns time and again to its core theme, sublimation of relationships. Here the warmth of the relationship between Elf and Human, between Human and Dwarf, their senses of trust and mutual respect is underline again and again. The main of the series may be the establishment of goodness, but goodness is shown here through human relations.

The series talks about the immortality of friendship where two friends value the promise made to each other more than family.

For them friendship is bigger than any relationship friendship is a unique thing, this sonnet of shakespeare is important based on its unbreakable bond.

"You are my all -the- world, and I must strive, to know my shames and praises form your tongue. In so profound abysm I throw all care of others voices, that my adder's sense to critic and to flattered stopped are"¹ This story is about the search for the bad guy, about his power. During the search, it is learned that the Elf species is in danger and only the Dwarves can protect that species because they have a special king of stone. Here once again realizing the bond of friendship and its power, the prince of the darts exerts all his might to save his friend.

Rumi writes about his feeling of friendship and love like this-

"In your light I learn How to love.

In you beauty, how to make poems.

you dance inside my chest,

where no one sees you,

but sometimes I do,

and that sight becomes this art"²

Here galadriel's Army is badly defeated. Thousands of people have died. The entire army of 'Numinar' is gone. Nori has gone with her companions to the south mountain, accompanied by her strange friend. Friend are not good or bad they are just friends. Nori and the strange's friendship reveals the most beautiful definition of humanity.

How even bad people become good in good company can be understood by looking at the stranger living with Nori.

The role of friendship is most important in Hollywood movies. The Harry potter series was also a story of friendship, courage and trust of three friends. There was also a battle between

darkness and light. Harry talkis about the some power of friendship while fighting his enemy- "you are the weak one, and you will never know love or friendship..... and I feel sorry for you".³

Nori's world was limited, his people lived in groups to be safe but Nori's curiosity, his yearning to see the would, separated him from other Dwarfs. Nori helped other's could put herself at risk for other's. In the story that follower's Galariel reflects on her past, never forgetting the loss of her brother and husband. She wants to completely eliminate her enemy.

Even after everything is over, one hope remains that hope is of victory, that hope is of goodness. And this is the end of the series where many secrets are revealed what Galadriel thought was the king of the south and was the 'Real Sairan' (the very evil that Galadriel has been searching for centuries). A Part of 'Sairan' who is Nori's friends. But he has no idea of his own strength, he has forgotten everything. There three rings are made to protect the Elf species. The rings that symbolized the light. Nori travels with her strange friend to help him, and thus ends this take of the magical power of the three rings.

This film is the story of ring making but human relationship have been carved with full sensitivity in it. This is a story of humanity, of friendship, of mutual understanding and love. This is a story of hope, of fighting together against the darkness.

REFERENCE

- [1] The sonnets of william shakespeare, G.P. Putnam's sons, New York and London.
- [2] My favourite Rumi, Selected by Jason Espaela.
- [3] <https://screenrant.com>